

IMPROVING THE CREATIVE APPROACH IN THE FORMATION OF ECOLOGICAL CONCEPTS IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The article aims to improve the creative approach to the formation of ecological concepts in primary school students, that is, ecological knowledge, values, skills and abilities, views and beliefs that ensure the formation of a responsible attitude towards the environment, in short, the ecological concept that regulates the diverse activities of students in the natural and social environment and the main task is to inculcate morals.*

Keywords: *ecology, ecological knowledge, nature protection, education, creativity, moral education, teaching process, creative approach, primary school students.*

The unity of theoretical ecological knowledge (ecological thinking) and activities in the field of environment and nature protection serve to form ecological culture. Ecological thinking is the mental expression of concepts regarding the current state of nature and the environment, their protection, and it is manifested as a complex socio-psychological phenomenon. Ecological activity means a set of actions performed to ensure nature and environment protection based on ecological knowledge.

Establishing the correct attitude towards nature in students, instilling love, achieving environmental cleanliness is an important step in the way of solving environmental problems. Ecological education is an educational process aimed at providing students with theoretical ecological knowledge in a consistent, systematic and continuous manner.

High spiritual perfection, selfless work for the country's freedom, prosperity, and people's well-being, being demanding towards oneself and others, being able to cultivate self-willed qualities, aspiration, initiative, organization, creativity, and independent thinking are considered as the most important principles in the life of our country. can be acknowledged. From this point of view, the concept of environmental education has been developed in our country and the adoption of this document is significant as it creates an important socio-cultural and legal basis for ensuring the environmental safety of the population.

Some features of the surrounding objects and events are perceived as a result of being organized and combined into integrated images. In elementary grades, cognitive weaknesses are encountered in the early stages of education. Perception of space, time and movement in children of junior school age is carried out with the help of the teacher during the educational process. Through his senses, he can perceive some features of the world: color, taste, smell. As a result of the arrangement of some of these features, he perceives the universe as a whole. Perceived things and events are embodied in a person's imagination. For example, when you hear the word apple, you imagine its taste.

The process of creativity in the formation of concepts of ecology among elementary school students is the reflection of rules of conduct, criteria, as well as the idea of national independence

in the minds of students. Creativity, moral activity skills and moral culture are established in the process of education and training on moral, socio-ideological, economic, legal, aesthetic and environmental topics, discussions, debates, selflessly working in various fields of the national economy, science, culture, development effective use of information about the lives and activities of people who make the name of the Republic of Uzbekistan world-famous by achieving high-level successes in the fields of publishing and sports, who make a worthy contribution to the increase of its prestige, are formed on the example of national heroes who have shown examples of patriotism.

In fact, the goal of teaching natural science to elementary school students based on a creative approach is to form concepts related to environmental education during the teaching process. Achieving this goal is a complex and multifaceted process, which is solved by abandoning consumerist attitudes towards nature, inculcating responsibility for the natural and man-made environment in the growing young generation.

In the process of teaching primary school subjects, the formation of concepts related to ecological education is dialectical knowledge that interprets the harmony of nature and society as a natural-historical, progressive, social problem. Man not only moves various types of plants and animals, plants and factories to other places, but also fundamentally changes the climate and ecology of the place where he lives. But at the current stage of society's development, environmental problems are interpreted as an actual social problem that does not depend on the system. Therefore, in the process of teaching natural science in elementary grades, the formation of concepts related to ecological education, in the education of pupils' responsibility for the environment, in the determination of universal and ethical-ecological values, relying on the ideas of ecological education regarding the conduct of morals, prudence, thrift, cleanliness, health, farming and animal husbandry is important.

The methodological basis of forming the concepts of environmental education in the teaching of natural science to elementary school students covers the following content:

- the essence of the student's personality is manifested in the set of interactions between nature, society and technology;
- forming a responsible attitude towards nature and the environment is an important goal of primary education, which shows that the student's personality has matured in all aspects;
- responsible attitude to nature is formed on the basis of harmonious development of its various: social, economic, spiritual, educational, ideological, political, legal aspects.

In the current period of accelerated scientific and technical development, in the process of coordinating and harmonizing the interaction and connection between nature and society, such environmental problems have arisen that they are interpreted as an urgent social, economic, spiritual, educational, ideological, political, and legal problem of our time.

Today, in the course of education, the formation of concepts related to environmental education among elementary school students has become an urgent necessity. The deepening environmental crisis has a negative impact on the development of our country. For example, it is becoming difficult to start farming and animal husbandry due to unfavorable natural factors, the living conditions of the population are becoming difficult due to the deterioration of the environment and the quality of drinking water, and the incidence of various diseases is increasing.

We aim to form concepts related to environmental education in elementary science classes. To achieve this goal, the following is necessary:

- to determine the size and content of the relevant materials of the concepts of environmental education in the teaching of natural science;
- development of a system of formation of interdisciplinary ecological concepts;
- to find ways, forms, methods and means of formation of concepts related to interdisciplinary environmental education among elementary school students.

Today, in the educational process, the formation of students' concepts of environmental education has become an urgent necessity. The deepening environmental crisis has a negative impact not only on the global scale, but also on the development of our country. For example, it is becoming difficult to start farming and animal husbandry due to unfavorable natural factors, the living conditions of the population are becoming difficult due to the deterioration of the environment and the quality of drinking water, and the incidence of various diseases is increasing. Although the main cause of such an ecological crisis is natural processes, they were created under the influence of anthropogenic factor - human activity. Therefore, it is not appropriate to assess this crisis as a purely natural-historical, gradual process or to attribute it to the lack of water.

In short, protecting the environment from various ecological problems is one of the urgent problems of today. To find a solution to these problems, it is important to provide ecological education to students with the concepts of ecological education and to educate them ecologically on the basis of creativity in order to ensure ecological literacy.

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